

The effect of inflation, interest rates, working capital turnover, receivables turnover on share prices of property and real estate sub-sector companies listed on the IDX

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the Effects of Inflation, Interest Rates, Working Capital Turnover, and Receivables Turnover on Share Prices in Property and Real Estate subsector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2018-2022 period. The background of this research arises from the need for further understanding of the economic and financial factors that may affect stock prices in the property and real estate sectors. This study uses a quantitative approach with a population of all property and real estate subsector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, totaling 85 companies. The research sample was taken by purposive sampling method, and the number of samples set was 10 companies. Data was collected from the annual financial statements of these companies during the study period. The data analysis method used is a regression test with a t test to see the influence of variables partially, an F test to see the influence simultaneously, and a coefficient of determination (R²) test to find out how much variation in Stock Prices can be explained by independent variables. The results showed that Inflation, Interest Rates, and Working Capital Turnover had a significant influence on Stock Price, while Receivables Turnover did not have a significant influence. Simultaneously, these four variables have a significant influence on the Share Price of Property and Real Estate subsector companies.

Keywords: Inflation; Interest Rate; Working Capital Turnover; Receivables Turnover; Stock Price

1. Introduction

Stock prices as one of the main indicators in the capital market, have a significant impact on investment decisions. When the stock price is high, it reflects the positive performance of the company and encourages investor interest in buying shares. Conversely, a low stock price can raise concerns about the company's performance, potentially reducing investor interest. Internal and external factors, including economic, political, and social conditions, influence stock price fluctuations. A company's financial and operational performance has an impact on the share price, with turnover and profit growth usually leading to an increase in share price, while poor performance can result in a price decline. Macroeconomic factors, such as interest rates, inflation, and economic growth, also play a role in stock pricing. According to Fatmawati and [1], the determination of a company's stock price can be measured by the final value (closing price) of investments, individual liabilities, or assets in the company. This limited company approach is a consistent application in the Indonesian capital market.

[2] explained that stock prices are determined by market participants based on supply and demand in the stock market at a certain time. Positive developments in the market and economy support an increase in stock prices, while investor sentiment and perceptions can affect stock prices. Good news or market optimism can push stock prices up, while bad news or uncertainty can cause a decline. Changes in government regulations related to industry or finance also have an impact on stock prices, with new policies creating uncertainty. Stock price fluctuations can occur in a short period of time and affect the stability of the capital market as a whole. Therefore, understanding the factors that affect stock prices

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is key in making investment decisions. Data on share prices of property and real estate sub-sector companies during the period 2018-2022 are also important considerations in this analysis.

Based on information from www.idx.co.id, it can be seen that the trend of stock price value development fluctuates every year. In 2023, there was a significant decrease of 55.52%, but in the following two years, there was an increase of 83.58% in 2022. Of the 10 issuers observed, their share prices fluctuated, showing variations in increases and decreases. However, there is a difference in KBAG issuers, where their share prices have remained stable for three periods, namely from 2020 to 2022, with a constant value of IDR 50. The stock price recorded the lowest development value for five years in 2020, which was 55.32%. The importance of an increasing stock price indicates a positive investment. An increase in stock price reflects an increase in the value of the investment and provides profit potential for investors. In addition, rising stock prices can also reflect positive company developments as well as market confidence in future prospects.

The capital market has a complex relationship with a company's share price, which can have a positive or negative impact. On the plus side, an efficient capital market can give companies access to the capital necessary for growth and expansion. The impact can be seen in the increase in the company's stock price due to investor optimism about the company's prospects. However, on the other hand, changes in market conditions, such as economic weakness or changes in interest rates, can lead to a decline in stock prices. Negative factors such as bad news or legal issues and poor financial performance can also have a negative impact on stock prices. Therefore, although sound capital markets provide significant access to funds, companies need to monitor market conditions and manage risks to minimize negative impacts on their share prices. In addition, inflation is also a critical factor as a macroeconomic indicator that reflects the health of the people's economy. Conditions in which commodity prices generally increase, causing economic weakness and a decrease in people's purchasing power. Data on inflation developments during the 2018-2022 period also provide an overview of economic conditions that deserve attention.

Based on data from Bank Indonesia, it can be seen that the inflation rate has increased significantly during the 2018-2022 period. From -13.10% in 2019, this figure increased to 194.65% in 2022. The lowest inflation rate was recorded in 2020 at 1.68%, while the highest inflation rate occurred in 2022 with a figure reaching 5.51. The relationship between inflation and stock prices can be complex and dependent on a variety of factors. In general, inflation according to [3], refers to the increase in the general price level of goods and services in a certain period of time. This phenomenon can be considered as a monetary aspect that reflects a decrease in the value of the currency used in the valuation of a product. The modern definition states that inflation is the increase in the total value of currency paid for goods, products, and services. Low or stable inflation tends to have a positive impact on stock prices. This situation reflects a healthy economy and provides stability for the business world. This positive impact can boost investor confidence, which in turn can push up stock prices. Conversely, high or unstable inflation tends to negatively impact stock prices because it can create uncertainty and harm economic stability. Therefore, understanding inflation conditions and their impact on the stock market is important for investors in making the right investment decisions.

Interest rates have a significant impact on a company's profitability, either increasing or decreasing the profits that can be obtained. In this study, the parameter assessed is the base interest rate, specifically the BI-Rate. Meanwhile, inflation is also closely related to interest rates, where an increase in the inflation rate can lead to an increase in interest rates. These two factors are interrelated and become a major concern for business people, especially in the goods production sector. According to [4], the possibility of changes in interest rates can have an impact on investment returns and potentially affect stock prices negatively. Interest rate risk, as explained by [5], arises from current fluctuations in market interest rates. In addition, [6] revealed that the rise and fall of bank interest rates can affect people's decisions, where rising interest rates encourage people to keep their money in banks, while lowering interest rates can encourage people to use the capital to buy shares. According to Bank Indonesia data for 2023, the lowest interest rate was recorded in 2021, at 3.5%. From the data table, it can be seen that the highest interest rate occurred in 2018, reaching 6%, and experienced a continuous decline in the following years. However, in 2022, there was an increase in interest rates to 5.5%, after a decline in the previous few years.

Working capital becomes a very significant element in designing the internal policy of an enterprise. Every business requires working capital to run its operations, including purchasing raw materials, paying employee salaries, and various other needs. The hope is that the funds spent on these activities can be reinvested through product sales. The working capital obtained from the sale will be used to fund other operational activities, and this cycle will continue in each business period. The importance of maintaining the proportion of working capital in accordance with business needs is crucial. The use of working capital that is less than necessary can cause losses to the business, while if it is too much, the amount of unused capital can be significant, indicating inefficient use of capital. According to [7], working capital turnover reflects the relationship between working capital, sales, and the amount of sales per rupiah of working

capital. Low working capital turnover may indicate an excess of working capital, which may be due to low inventory turnover, receivables, or excessive cash balances. In addition, working capital can be obtained from third-party loans, but interest costs must be taken into account. Efficient management of funds can make a positive contribution to the company's profits and overall company value.

In addition to capital turnover, an important parameter that is often used to measure the effectiveness of working capital in company operations is accounts receivable, which arise as a result of credit sales. Imbalances in the receivables control system can cause working capital to be ineffective, especially if there are bad debts that can disrupt the company's liquidity and business operations. Therefore, separate evaluation of receivables is important to ensure that receivables can be managed smoothly, measured, and can improve working capital efficiency. Receivables turnover itself is a ratio that links net sales with receivables, calculated by dividing net sales by the average net receivables [8]. Receivables turnover is highly dependent on receivables control systems, such as payment terms, where strong payment conditions can accelerate receivables turnover and vice versa.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Research Approach

The analysis used in this study is quantitative analysis. [9] defines quantitative research as a research method that uses numerical data collected through research tools such as questionnaires or tests, then analyzed using statistical techniques. Quantitative research can be used to test hypotheses, compare variables, and explore relationships between variables. In addition, quantitative research can also be used to make generalizations to a larger population.

2.2 Population and Sample

The research population is the entire individual, object, or event that is the focus of research and can provide the information needed to answer the research question. The study population can be humans, animals, plants, inanimate objects, or social phenomena that you want to study. The study population studied is the entire research subject. In this study, the population is all Property and Real Estate Sub-Sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange with a total of 85 companies.

Samples are some members of groups or objects that are used as a basis for obtaining information or conclusions from the group studied. Research samples are taken by purposive sampling method which is carried out by taking subjects not based on class strata, random or area based on certain criteria. Then samples that have met the predetermined requirements, namely as many as 10 companies are sample.

2.3 Data Analysis Techniques

2.3.1 Panel Data Regression Analysis

This analysis estimates how the state of a dependent variable increases and decreases in value when two or more independent variables are manipulated as predictors (increasing and decreasing values). Therefore, multiple regression analysis is performed when the number of independent variables is two or more. In general, the regression format used for multiple linear regression with an error rate of 5% is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + e$$

Information:

Y = Dependent variable (Stock Price)

α = Constant coefficient

β_1 = Inflation Rate Regression Coefficient

X1 = Variable Inflation Rate

β_2 = Interest Rate Regression Coefficient

X2 = Variable Interest Rate

β_3 = Regression coefficient of working capital turnover

X3 = Working Capital Turnover Variable

β_4 = Regression coefficient of Receivables Turnover

X4 = Variable Receivables Turnover

E = Level error

2.3.2 Test the hypothesis

Hypothesis testing involves making two hypotheses, namely the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis. The null hypothesis states that there is no difference or relationship between the variables tested, whereas the alternative hypothesis states the opposite. Then, data sampling is carried out and testing of the null hypothesis is carried out using appropriate statistical techniques. If the test results show that the null hypothesis can be rejected, then the alternative hypothesis is acceptable. However, if the test results are not strong enough to reject the null hypothesis, then the null hypothesis is still accepted. The hypothesis tests used are the t test, F test and coefficient of determination (R²).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Statistical descriptions can act as a first step in analyzing panel data before proceeding to the panel data model estimation stage. Descriptive statistics help uncover the basic characteristics of panel data, including center size, data distribution, and frequency distribution of observed variables, as shown in the following table.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistical Test

Date: 12/23/23 Time: 14:46					
Sample: 2018 2022					
	INFLASI_X1	TINGKAT_SUKU_BUNGA_X2	PERPUTRAN_MODAL_KE_RJA_X3	PERPUTARAN_PIUTANG_X4	HARGA_SAHAM_Y
Mean	2.982000	4.750000	-5.231000	22.65860	711.0500
Median	2.720000	5.000000	0.290000	10.50000	266.5000
Maximum	5.510000	6.000000	17.01000	359.7900	11100.00
Minimum	1.680000	3.500000	-289.8400	0.450000	50.00000
Std. Dev.	1.386015	0.984575	41.28645	51.83365	1660.160
Skewness	0.972392	-0.121497	-6.746336	5.723744	5.281704
Kurtosis	2.553441	1.374654	47.02918	37.38608	32.50880
Jarque-Bera	8.294997	5.626660	4417.961	2736.349	2046.572
Probability	0.015804	0.060005	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	149.1000	237.5000	-261.5500	1132.930	35552.50
Sum Sq. Dev.	94.13080	47.50000	83523.98	131649.7	1.35E+08
Observations	50	50	50	50	50

Source: Eviews11 Data Management (2024)

In the results of descriptive statistical tests, there are characteristics that reflect the distribution and variability of data from the observed variables. The mean is an indicator of the size of the data center, and from these results it can be seen that the average of Inflation X1 is around 2.982, Interest Rate X2 is around 4.75, Working Capital Turnover X3 is around -5.231, Receivables Turnover X4 is around 22.65860, and Share Price Y is around 711.0500. Furthermore, the median value gives an idea of the median value of the data, which shows that the median value of Inflation is around 2,720, Interest Rate is around 5,000, Working Capital Turnover is around 0.290, Receivables Turnover is around 10,500, and Stock Price is around 266,5000. In addition, the standard deviation (Std. Dev.) measures the spread of data, with the highest results found in Working Capital Turnover of around 41.28645 and Share Price of around 1660.160. However, it should be noted that some variables show extreme values, as seen in maximum and minimum values and kurtosis

which is quite high. For example, Receivables Turnover has a maximum value of about 359.7900 and a minimum value of only 0.450000, indicating a significant imbalance. High kurtosis values on some variables, especially Working Capital Turnover and Share Price, reflect that data distributions tend to have thicker tails and are heavier at extremes, signaling possible outliers or extreme values in the distribution. Therefore, the interpretation of the results of this descriptive statistical test needs to be done carefully and needs to be considered in further analysis of the panel data.

3.2 Model Specification Test

3.2.1 Test Chow

Table 2 Chow Test

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests			
Equation: Untitled			
Test cross-section fixed effects			
Effects Test	Statistics	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	18.588982	(9,36)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	86.558395	9	0.0000

Chow Test is used to choose between CEM or FEM models, in this study the results of the Chow Test have a cross section F probability value of 0.0000 which means the selected model is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) model. If (Prob < 0.05) means that H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted, then from the Chow Test the regression technique used is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

3.2.2 Hausman Test

Table 3 Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test			
Equation: Untitled			
Test cross-section random effects			
Test Summary	Chi-sq. Statistics	Chi-sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	0.000000	4	1.0000

Then, from the information above, it is known that the Hausman Test that has been carried out is invalid, this is because one of the independent variables of the research data does not meet the requirements for a random effect. Meanwhile, if the research data does not meet the requirements for a random effect, the eviews program will reject the Hausman Test, so it can be concluded that clearly the Fixed Effect Method is better. For this reason, it is necessary to do the next test, namely the Lenglange Multiplier Test.

3.3 Panel Data Regression Analysis

After testing the overall model, the selected model is the FEM regression test model which can be seen in the following table.

Based on the results of data processing in table 3., it can be seen that: Mean PBV of 1.508095 can be interpreted as the stock price in the market is 1.508095 higher than the book value, this condition can be said to be good. The highest PBV value was 8.72 and the lowest was 0.00. DER has a mean value of 6.714667. The mean DER of 6.714667 can be interpreted as the company's capital structure comes from higher liabilities of 6.714667 compared to equity. The highest DER value was 35.47 and the lowest value was 0.49. PER has a mean value of 15.66438. The mean PER of 15.66438 can mean that the stock price in the market is 15.66438 higher than earnings per share. The highest PER value was 227.27 and the lowest value was -92. ROA has a mean value of 1.461619. The mean ROA of 1.461619 can be

interpreted from the use of total assets resulting in a net income of 1.461619. The highest ROA value was 12.98 and the lowest value was -43.76.

Table 4 Panel Data Multiple Linear Test

Dependent Variable: HARGA_SAHAM_Y				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 12/23/23 Time: 14:48				
Sample: 2018 2022				
Periods included: 5				
Cross-sections included: 10				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 50				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.584020	0.732944	6.254261	0.0000
INFLASI_X1	-0.640813	0.260939	-2.455800	0.0190
TINGKAT_SUKU_BUNGA_X2	1.330159	0.567264	2.344867	0.0247
PERPUTRAN_MODAL_KERJA_X3	0.137928	0.062974	2.190250	0.0351
PERPUTARAN_PIUTANG_X4	-0.144109	0.090742	-1.588122	0.1210
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.856816	Mean dependent var	5.704689	
Adjusted R-squared	0.805111	S.D. dependent var	1.191306	
S.E. of regression	0.525917	Akaike info criterion	1.784148	
Sum squared resid	9.957179	Schwarz criterion	2.319514	
Log likelihood	-30.60370	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.988018	
F-statistic	16.57117	Durbin-Watson stat	2.086694	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Eviews11 Data Management (2024)

$$Y = a + bx_1 + bx_2 + bx_3 + bx_4 + e$$

$$Y = 4.584020 + 0.640813X_1 + 1.330159X_2 + 0.137928X_3 - 0.144109X_4 + e$$

The equation can be explained if the constant is 4.584020 meaning that if variables X1 to X4 are zero (0) or the value is fixed, then the variable Y has a value of 4.584020.

The regression coefficient of variable X1 of -0.640813 means that an increase in variable X1 by 1 unit will cause a decrease in variable Y by -0.640813 units. The coefficient is negative which means that the direction of the relationship between variable X1 and variable Y is not in the same direction that if variable X1 goes up, variable Y goes down and vice versa. The regression coefficient of variable X2 of 1.330159 means that an increase in variable X2 by 1 unit will cause an increase in variable Y by 1.330159 units. The coefficient is positive, which means that the direction of the relationship between variable X2 and variable Y is unidirectional, which if variable X2 rises, variable Y rises, and vice versa.

The regression coefficient of variable X3 of 0.137928 means that an increase in variable X3 by 1 unit will cause an increase in variable Y by 0.137928 units. The coefficient is positive, which means that the direction of the relationship between variable X3 and variable Y is unidirectional, if variable X3 rises, variable Y rises, and vice versa. The regression coefficient of variable X4 is -0.144109, meaning that there is an increase in variable X4 by 1 unit, it will cause a decrease

in variable Y by -0.144109 units. The coefficient is negative which means that the direction of the relationship between variable X4 and variable Y is not in the same direction that if variable X4 goes up, variable Y goes down and vice versa.

3.4 Test the Hypothesis

3.4.1 T Test

The t test is used to determine whether there is a significant influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable which is explained as follows.

Table 5 Partial t-test

Dependent Variable: HARGA_SAHAM_Y				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 12/23/23 Time: 14:48				
Sample: 2018 2022				
Periods included: 5				
Cross-sections included: 10				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 50				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.584020	0.732944	6.254261	0.0000
INFLASI_X1	-0.640813	0.260939	-2.455800	0.0190
TINGKAT_SUKU_BUNGA_X2	1.330159	0.567264	2.344867	0.0247
PERPUTRAN_MODAL_KERJA_X3	0.137928	0.062974	2.190250	0.0351
PERPUTARAN_PIUTANG_X4	-0.144109	0.090742	-1.588122	0.1210

Source: Eviews11 Data Processing (2024)

$$t\text{-Table } (n-k-1) = (50-4-1) = t\text{-Table } 45 = 2.01410$$

Based on the t test table above, the influence of variable X1 on variable Y is $0.0190 < 0.050$ while for the t value calculate $-2.455800 < t$ table (2.01410), where H_0 is rejected and hypothesis 1 is accepted. This means that inflation partially has a negative and significant effect on the Share Price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022.

Based on the t-test table above, the effect of variable X2 on variable Y is $0.0247 < 0.050$, while for the value of t calculate $2.344867 > t$ table (2.01410), where H_0 is rejected and Hypothesis 2 is accepted. This means that the Interest Rate partially has a positive and significant effect on the Share Price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022.

Based on the t-test table above, the effect of variable X3 on variable Y is $0.0351 < 0.050$ while for the value of t calculate $2.190250 > t$ table (2.01410), where H_0 is rejected and Hypothesis 3 is accepted. This means that the Working Capital Turnover partially has a positive and significant effect on the Share Price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022.

Based on the t test table above, the influence of variable X4 on variable Y is $0.1210 > 0.050$ while for the t value calculate $-1.588122 < t$ table (2.01410), where H_0 is accepted and Hypothesis 4 is rejected. This means that the partial Receivables Turnover has no effect and is not significant on the Share Price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022.

3.5 Test F

Table 6 Simultaneous Test F

R-squared	0.856816	Mean dependent var	5.704689
Adjusted R-squared	0.805111	S.D. dependent var	1.191306
S.E. of regression	0.525917	Akaike info criterion	1.784148
Sum squared resid	9.957179	Schwarz criterion	2.319514
Log likelihood	-30.60370	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.988018
F-statistic	16.57117	Durbin-Watson stat	2.086694
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Eviews11 Data Management (2024)

$$F\text{-Table} = (n-k) = (50-4) = F\text{-Table } 46 = 2.57$$

Based on the table above, it is known that the calculated F value is greater than the table F value ($16.57117 > 2.57$), with a significance value of $0.000000 < 0.05$. Thus, H_0 is rejected Hypothesis 5 is accepted which means that Inflation, Interest Rates, Working Capital Turnover and Receivables Turnover simultaneously have a significant effect on the Share Price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018-2022.

3.6 Test Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 7 R² Coefficient of Determination Test

R-squared	0.856816	Mean dependent var	5.704689
Adjusted R-squared	0.805111	S.D. dependent var	1.191306
S.E. of regression	0.525917	Akaike info criterion	1.784148
Sum squared resid	9.957179	Schwarz criterion	2.319514
Log likelihood	-30.60370	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.988018
F-statistic	16.57117	Durbin-Watson stat	2.086694
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Eviews11 Data Management (2024)

From the table of results above, it can be seen that the value of R Squared is 0.856816 or 85.68%. This number shows the magnitude of the influence of variables X1 to X4 on Variable Y combined, while the remaining 14.32% is influenced by other variable factors outside this study or error values.

4. Conclusion

- The Effect of Inflation on Stock Prices

Depending on the signals sent to the market, inflation can have a positive or negative impact on stock prices. When inflation is seen as a positive signal of strong economic growth, stock prices can rise due to higher corporate profit expectations. H_0 was rejected and hypothesis 1 was accepted, namely that inflation partially has a negative and significant effect on stock prices in Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022. If inflation is seen as a negative signal, there is economic instability and stock prices may fall due to increased uncertainty.

- The Effect of Interest Rates on Stock Prices

If interest rates rise, this could be seen as a negative signal for the market. Rising interest rates signal that the central bank is trying to stem inflation or curb overly rapid economic growth. In response to these negative signals, stock prices tend to fall as investors lose confidence in the company's future earnings growth. Rising interest rates also increase a

company's cost of debt, which can lower net income and shareholder value. As a result, the company's share price may be negatively impacted by rising interest rates. H_0 was rejected and hypothesis 2 was accepted, namely that the Interest Rate partially had a positive and significant effect on the share price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022. If it has a positive effect, interest rates fall, so this can encourage economic growth or drive investment.

- The Effect of Working Capital Turnover on Stock Prices

When the company manages to maintain a high level of working capital turnover, it can be considered a positive signal for the market. A high level of working capital turnover indicates that the company is able to manage its assets efficiently, has good liquidity, and can reduce the risk of failure to meet its short-term obligations. In response to these positive signals, stock prices tend to rise as investors have more confidence in the company's performance and future earnings prospects. H_0 was rejected and hypothesis 3, namely Working Capital Turnover, partially has a positive and significant effect on the share price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022.

- The Effect of Receivables Turnover on Stock Prices

If the company manages to maintain a high rate of receivables turnover, this can be considered a positive signal for the market. A high receivables turnover rate indicates that the company is able to manage credit risk well, has good liquidity, and can convert receivables into cash quickly. In response to these positive signals, stock prices tend to rise as investors have more confidence in the company's performance and future earnings prospects. H_0 was accepted and Hypothesis 4 was rejected, namely that the partial receivables turnover had no effect and was not significant on the share price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018 – 2022.

- Effects of Inflation, Interest Rates, Working Capital Turnover, and Receivables Turnover on Stock Prices

H_0 rejected hypothesis 5 accepted namely Inflation, Interest Rates, Working Capital Turnover and Receivables Turnover simultaneously have a significant effect on the Share Price of Property and Real Estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018-2022. If inflation, interest rates, working capital turnover, and receivables turnover have a significant influence on stock prices, it indicates that these factors provide important signals to the market and reflect the company's effective management policies in managing risk, liquidity, and operational efficiency. Thus, changes in these factors can significantly affect the stock price and provide investors with valuable information regarding the company's performance and its future prospects.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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